

A Vibrational Spectroscopic Study of the Vibrations of Hydroxamic Acid and its Derivatives in Solid State

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Solid state Raman and infrared spectral study of benzydroxamic acid, potassium salt of benzydroxamic acid and *N*-benzophenylhydroxamic acid, in the frequency range 500–1700 cm^{-1} , have been made along with a reference molecule, benzamide. From a comparative study of the different spectra of the compounds, each having the common feature in presence one or more phenyl ring in their structures, the various planar vibrations due to the phenyl ring and those originating from the substituent groups have been identified.

Infrared spectra of hydroxamic derivatives including benzydroxamic acid and *N*-benzophenylhydroxamic acid in KBr matrix were studied by Hadzi and Prevorsek¹. They proposed the assignments of the absorption bands to specific vibrational modes in the molecules containing hydroxamic acid groups. To make a complete assignment, besides the infrared spectra, the Raman spectra (500–1700 cm^{-1}) of the compounds, viz. benzydroxamic acid (BHA), potassium salt of benzydroxamic acid (KBHA) and *N*-benzophenylhydroxamic acid (NBPHA) in the polycrystalline powder form, have been recorded and their spectral features analysed. Such study with benzamide (BA) molecule have also been carried out, treating it as a reference molecule. While assigning the observed bands, some interesting features have been noticed and they have been explained based on the present experimental data.

Results and Discussion

The Raman spectra of the compounds, studied presently, are shown in Fig. 1 and their structures in Fig. 2. All the molecules contain at least one phenyl ring part, denoted by ϕ , and another part containing carbonyl and other atomic groups. Assignments of the frequencies due to vibrations of the two parts are considered separately. The vibration frequencies due to $\nu_{\text{C-H}}$, $\nu_{\text{N-H}}$ and $\nu_{\text{O-H}}$ have been excluded as their usual ranges of appearances are beyond the present investigated spectral region. The coupling between the vibrational modes of two phenyl rings in NBPHA is not expected to be strong and accordingly, the spectrum should be similar to that of a single phenyl ring.

Phenyl ring vibrations : The molecules, studied, at best, may belong to the point group C_{2v} , and in the frequency range, studied presently, the phenyl ring part molecules should have 16 planar vibrations. But one of them, a C–H deformation mode (vibration frequency 1037 cm^{-1} in ben-

Fig. 1. Raman shifts (cm^{-1}) of (a) potassium salt of benzydroxamic acid (KBHA), (b) benzydroxamic acid (BHA), (c) benzamide (BA) and (d) *N*-benzophenylhydroxamic acid (NBPHA).

zene) is very much sensitive to substitution resulting in reduction in its frequency value to the region 200–400 cm^{-1} in mono-substituted benzenes². Other vibrations, expected, are 6 in-plane C : C stretching, 3 in-plane C : C deformation mode and 1 C–H stretching mode converted into C–substituent bond stretching vibration. The assignments, are similar to those for mono-substituted benzene molecules³. These are shown in Table 1.

Substituent group vibrations : After the phenyl ring vibrations are assigned (Table 1), the remaining bands in the infrared and the Raman spectra of the molecules can reasonably be attributed to the planar vibrations of the substituent groups in each molecule. From Fig. 2, it is evident

Fig. 2. Structural formulae of BA, BHA, KBHA, NBPHA.

that $\nu_{C=O}$ and ν_{C-N} modes are expected in all cases except KBHA. In the molecule of benzamide there will be one NH_2 deformation and one NH_2 wagging modes, while in BHA only one $N-H$ in-plane deformation frequency is expected. The molecule of KBHA is expected to show frequencies due to the stretching vibrational modes of $C=N$ and $C-O$ bonds. Moreover, there will be frequencies arising from $N-O$ stretching⁴ and $O-H$ planar deformation modes in all the molecules except benzamide.

Carbonyl stretching frequency: This frequency in normal carbonyl molecules generally occurs around 1700 cm^{-1} in both Raman and infrared spectra. Its position in condensed phase is, however, shifted to lower values by different amounts due to hydrogen bonding conjugation and/or resonance. In the infrared spectra of BA, the strong band at 1615 cm^{-1} most probably represent the NH_2 scissoring mode. A vibration frequency at 1614 cm^{-1} in 2,6-dichloroaniline⁶ had been assigned to this mode. In KBHA, there will be no carbonyl frequency and none is observed. In NBPHA, there is a moderately strong Raman band at 1627 cm^{-1} and a strong infrared absorption at 1622 cm^{-1} . These

bands presumably represent $\nu_{C=O}$ mode in the molecule. No doubling of this band either in Raman or infrared spectra has been observed as claimed by Hadzi and Prevorsek¹. From Fig. 1, it is seen that the Raman bands due to $\nu_{C=O}$ mode are absent in both BHA or BA in crystalline powder form, which seems very significant. Equally significant is the non-appearance of the band due to δ_{NH_2} mode in the spectrum of BA molecule. It may be noted that neither $\nu_{C=O}$ nor δ_{NH_2} had been reported in the Raman spectrum of benzamide crystals⁸. A tentative explanation of the non-appearance of any frequency due to $\nu_{C=O}$ mode in BA and BHA may be offered by considering that the amide group has a large contribution from resonance structures (I and II), which weakens the $C=O$ bond and stiffens the $C-N$ bond as per scheme, shown below :

Hence, the double bond in carbonyl group is not a pure double bond as a result of which, though the asymmetric charge distribution causes a change in dipole moment rendering the concerned vibration infrared active with reduced frequency, but the associated Raman band could not be detected as they are too weak for detection due to a probable insignificant change in polarisability during the vibration of the mode in the solid state. Due to stiffening of the $C-N$ bond in structure II, δ_{NH_2} mode is very weak for

TABLE I—IMPORTANT PLANAR VIBRATIONAL FREQUENCIES (cm^{-1}) OF THE PHENYL RING

BA		BHA		KBHA		NBPHA		Assignment
Raman	Ir	Raman	Ir	Raman	Ir	Raman	Ir	
-	532(s)	520(2)	530(m)	516(8)	516(m)	515(2)	508(w)	$\alpha_{C:C}$
614(4)	618(ms)	619(20)	621(w)	618(m)	620(w)	618(m)	620(w)	$\alpha_{C:C}$
773(7)	770(vs)	750(30)	790(vs)	794(5)	794(m)	790(7)	790(s)	$\alpha_{C:C}$
1001(32)	1001(w)	1001(80)	-	1000(60)	-	997(38)	1000(m)	$\nu_{C:C}$
1023(6)	1020(s)	1027(5)	1025(s)	1030(4)	1026(s)	1024(11)	1030(m)	$\nu_{C:C}$
-	-	1039(21)	1045(m)	1041(8)	1048(s)	1058(2)	1052(s)	β_{C-H}
1143(6)	1140(m)	1161(14)	1165(s)	1160(10)	1160(s)	1169(8)	1160(s)	β_{C-H}
1170(34)	1175(w)	1185(3)	1185(w)	1181(12)	1184(m)	1185(5)	1182(m)	β_{C-H}
-	-	-	-	-	-	1238(4)	1238(m)	$\nu_{C\text{-subst}}$
-	-	-	-	-	-	1278(2)	1284(m)	β_{C-H}
1301(4)	1292(w)	-	1305(w)	-	-	1307(5)	1302(w)	$\nu_{C:C}$
1447(4)	1440(m)	1445(4)	1450(w)	1442(2)	1445(m)	1443(4)	1442(s)	$\nu_{C:C}$
-	1479(m)	1486(4)	1490(m)	1484(4)	1484(m)	1496(5)	1587(s)	$\nu_{C:C}$
1565(6)	1570(s)	1579(9)	1585(s)	1574(4)	1566(s)	-	1574(s)	$\nu_{C:C}$
1602(21)	1606(m)	1602(100)	1610(s)	1602(100)	1604(vs)	1592(37)	1590(s)	$\nu_{C:C}$

TABLE 2—PLANAR VIBRATIONS (cm^{-1}) OF THE SUBSTITUENT GROUP

BA		KBHA		BHA		NBPHA		Assignment
Raman	Ir	Raman	Ir	Raman	Ir	Raman	Ir	
—	—	897(21)	900(s)	900(17)	900(s)	—	900(S)	$\nu_{\text{N-O}}$
—	—	—	—	1306(92)	1304(s)	—	—	$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$
—	—	1316(38)	1315(s)	—	1320(m)	1322(5)	1320(m)	$\delta_{\text{O-H}}$
1411(4)	1395(s)	1327(47)	1328(s)	—	—	1364(5)	1370(vs)	$\nu_{\text{C-N}}$
—	—	—	—	1523(94)	1520(s)	—	—	$\nu_{\text{C=N}}$
—	—	1548(16)	1552(s)	—	—	—	—	$\delta_{\text{N-H}}$
—	1615(s)	—	—	—	—	—	—	$\delta_{\text{N-H}}$
—	1650(s)	—	1640(s)	—	—	1627(32)	1622(s)	$\nu_{\text{C=O}}$

detection in Raman spectrum of BHA. The crystallographic consideration of intermolecular interaction or stacking is likely to result in the formation of predominantly intermolecular hydrogen bonded dimer with a centre of symmetry when there should be two carbonyl stretching frequencies, symmetric and asymmetric. The symmetric one will be Raman-active and asymmetric counterpart infrared-active. But the non-appearance of at least symmetric $\nu_{\text{C=O}}$ mode which is expected to appear strongly in Raman spectrum rules out such a possibility. As both BA and BHA are insoluble in normal solvents like acetonitrile, methanol, chloroform, it has not been possible to extend the investigation to the study in solutions to find any plausible explanation for the non-appearance of carbonyl stretching band in BA and BHA.

Other vibrations : It has already been stated that there will be no frequency due to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ mode in KBHA, but it is expected to show the frequency due to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ vibration. It is known that this frequency normally occurs at $\approx 1650 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. However, in KBHA a very strong Raman band of somewhat lower shift appears at 1523 cm^{-1} (Fig. 1) with strong infrared counterpart at 1520 cm^{-1} . Since such a frequency does not appear in the spectra of the other molecules, it is attributed to $\nu_{\text{C=N}}$ mode in KBHA. The lower value of the frequency may be due to the fact that C=N bond is not a pure double bond because of the possible tautomeric mechanism (Fig. 3). In the Raman spectra of BHA the moderately strong Raman band at 1548 cm^{-1} with its infrared counterpart at 1552 cm^{-1} , probably represents the δ_{NH} mode. Hadzi and Prevorsek¹ designated this as amide II band. Among the other in-plane vibration frequencies of the substituent group, the unambiguous identification of

Fig. 3. Description of tautomeric mechanism.

$\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ and $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ and $\delta_{\text{C-H}}$ vibrations are rather difficult. However, the frequency due to $\nu_{\text{C-O}}$ mode can be identified in KBHA remembering that it usually appears in the spectral range $1320\text{--}1210 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ in many aromatic molecules⁹ containing the C-O group, viz. carboxylic acid and its esters. The frequency due to $\delta_{\text{O-H}}$ mode is likely to appear in all the molecules except BA. The $\delta_{\text{O-H}}$ vibrations are generally observed around 1300 cm^{-1} . Accordingly, in the present molecules the frequencies in the region $1315\text{--}1320 \text{ cm}^{-1}$ have been attributed to $\delta_{\text{O-H}}$ mode. In all the molecules except KBHA, there should be a frequency due to C-N stretching mode. In BA, there is a weak Raman band at 1411 cm^{-1} with a strong infrared counterpart at 1395 cm^{-1} . Since in the case of this molecule all other high frequency bands have been assigned satisfactorily, this frequency can reasonably be correlated with C-N bond stretching vibration. The frequency value of the vibration $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ is rather low in BHA while it is represented in NBPHA by the strong Raman band at 1364 cm^{-1} with a strong infrared counterpart at 1370 cm^{-1} . This infrared band has a companion at 1392 cm^{-1} appearing as a strong shoulder. Hadzi and Prevorsek¹ assigned the pair 1376 and 1396 cm^{-1} to $\nu_{\text{C-N}}$ modes in two crystalline forms of NBPHA. Since no Raman band other than that at 1364 cm^{-1} is noticed in the Raman spectrum of NBPHA in polycrystalline powder, the previous assignment¹ does not seem to have much credibility. The presently proposed assignments are shown in Table 2.

Experimental

Raman spectra of the compounds, in powder form, were obtained on a SPEX Laser Raman spectrophotometer (Ramalog) using 514.5 nm radiation from an Ar^+ Laser as the exciting radiation. The accuracy of measurements of sharp bands is $\pm 2 \text{ cm}^{-1}$. The infrared spectra (KBr) were recorded on a Perkin-Elmer 783 spectrophotometer.

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